

Experimentation of an optical prototype for monitoring the ripening of table tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L., Marinda F1) and oil olives (*Olea europaea* L.)

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The interest in new tools to follow the fruit and vegetable maturation process, recent need for simplified portable devices, and commercial availability of small-sized optical components give the opportunity to create an optical device based on light emitting diode (LED) technology, which will be tested in this work to monitor the ripening of table tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L., Marinda F1) and oil olives (*Olea europaea* L.). Optical analyses were carried out on 200 tomatoes and 200 oil olives. The main quality parameters (soluble solids content, moisture content, pH, and firmness) were measured as reference analyses for the tomato samples, while four arbitrary ripening classes for oil olives were created according to skin color: totally green (class 1), less than 50% purple/black surface (class 2), more than 50% purple/black surface (class 3), totally purple/black (class 4). Optical measurements were acquired by using an optical prototype developed by the Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences at the Università degli Studi di Milano, equipped with 12 LED at specific wavelengths, between 450 and 860 nm, chosen thanks to previous research. To verify the performance of the prototype, commercial portable spectrophotometers with a wavelength range from 350 nm to 2500 nm were used. In detail, partial least squares (PLS) and multi-linear regression (MLR) regression models were calculated for the estimation of tomato quality parameters, and partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) classification models were calculated for olive ripening class identification. Overall, the prototype shows lower performance than commercial devices using the entire spectrum, even if outcomes should be considered promising for further development towards the final engineering phase of the device.

Keywords: LED, device, spectroscopy, visible/near-infrared, chemometrics, pre-harvest

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